

Design & Analysis of Torsionally Loaded Statically Indeterminate Bimetallic Shaft

Complex Engineering Problem

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Abstract

The project focusses on design and analysis of statically indeterminate torsionally loaded shaft. Using the fundamentals of mechanics of materials the approach was designed. All the possible configurations for the design were considered taking unconventional approach by varying the radial ratios between the solid and hollow shaft. An algorithm was developed to find the best design based on the constraints and material utilisation. For FEA analysis ANSYS APDL was used to verify the results obtained. The maximum shear stress and twist occurred in the hollow shaft and it increases with decrease in radial ratio between shaft. The results obtained shows the behaviour of shaft under torsional loading with reasonable accuracy.

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1 Introduction

The bimetallic shafts are of great importance in the Engineering applications due to their enhanced properties. Bimetallic shafts are made up of two different metals with different structural properties that make them suitable for certain applications in Automotives and industrial processes

2 Problem Statement

The problem involves the design and analysis of bimetallic statically indeterminate torsionally loaded shaft. The design constraints in the problem involve the geometrical and material difference between different sections of the shaft. The shaft is loaded with with two opposite torques at different points having same magnitude. The shaft is fixed by both ends by fixed supports. The one section of circular shaft is solid while other is hollow.

Figure 1: Schematic of Bimetallic Shaft Subjected to Torque

3 Design Requirements

The design of shaft requires the following conditions to be fulfilled:

1. **Length Requirements:** The length of shaft is 2m with each point at equal distance of 0.5m from each other.
2. **Materials :** The design requires the solid shaft must be made with Aluminum 5456-H116 and hollow shaft with Aluminum 2014-T6.
3. **Geometry:** The inner diameter of the hollow section must be strictly less than the outer diameter of the solid section $r_{\text{solid}} > r_{\text{inner,hollow}}$. All dimensions must be whole numbers.
4. **Deformation:** The angle of twist at section CE must not greater than 1.5° .
5. **Factor of Safety:** A minimum factor of safety (FoS) of 2.5 must be taken in the design.

3.1 Assumptions

The following steps were followed in order to perform the analysis:

1. **Elastic Limit:** The material remains in the elastic limit so Hooks law is applied in analysis.

2. **Saint-Venant Principle :** The stresses remains constant throughout the shaft except the region of stress application.
3. **Homogeneity of Materials:** Both Aluminum 5456-H116 and Aluminum 2014-T6 are assumed to be homogeneous and isotropic materials.
4. **Deformation:** The angle of twist at section CE must not greater than 1.5° .
5. **Factor of Safety:** A minimum factor of safety (FoS) of 2.5 must be taken in the design.
6. **Negligible Deformation in Supports:** The angle of twist at the supports is considered negligible and taken as zero.
7. **Loading Conditions :** Only torsional load is considered on the shaft simplifying the analysis.

4 Design Limitation

The design limitations of the statically indeterminate torsionally loaded bimetallic shaft due to requirements and scope of study are as follows

1. **Material Constraints:** The ultimate shear strength and modulus of elasticity for both metals limits the maximum applied torque and stress that shaft can withstand without failing.
2. **Geometrical Constraints:** The inner diameter of the hollow section must be smaller than the outer diameter of the solid section. Additionally, all diameters must be whole numbers (X.00 mm).
3. **Angle of Twist:** Due to small angle of twist requirements the length and applied torques are restricted with in certain range.
4. **Failure Mechanism:** The failure mechanisms as creep, fatigue and torsional buckling are not considered limiting the scope of design.
5. **Factor of Safety:** A minimum factor of safety (FoS) of 2.5 must be maintained, ensuring that the shaft will not fail under extreme conditions it limits the applied loading conditions.
6. **Length Constraints:** The overall length of the shaft is constrained by the allowable angle of twist, limiting the design dimensions for the solid and hollow sections.
7. **Manufacturing Limitations:** The shaft's dimensions must be manufacturable, with a focus on tolerances for whole number diameters.
8. **Bonding of Dissimilar Metals:** The bonding of the solid and hollow sections (Aluminum 5456-H116 and Aluminum 2014-T6) requires suitable bonding mechanism as welding or diffusion bonding . The difference in material properties as thermal expansion coefficient of both materials can cause thermal stresses at interface of metals .

5 Methodology

The torsionally loaded bimetallic shaft design is studied from different approach considering all the possible configurations of shaft. The mathematical model developed for study includes the proper approach to reach the optimal design. The behaviour of structural properties with change in geometric relations is discussed in detail.

- **Case 1:** $r_{\text{solid}} = r_{\text{outer,hollow}}$

In the first case when outer radius of hollow and solid shaft are equal. The relation between the hollow shaft radial dimensions is taken as

$$r_{\text{outer}} = \kappa r_{\text{inner}}$$

$$\kappa > 1$$

Where κ is the radial ratio between the hollow shaft's outer and inner radii. As the value of κ changes, the structural properties of the shaft change significantly.

- **Case 2:** $r_{\text{solid}} > r_{\text{outer,hollow}}$

When the solid shaft is greater than hollow shaft onemore radial relation between solida nd hollow shaft outer radius as taken along with relation between hollow shaft radial dimensions.

$$r_{\text{outer}} = \kappa r_{\text{inner}}$$

$$\kappa > 1$$

$$r_{\text{solid}} = \eta r_{\text{outer,hollow}}$$

$$\eta > 1$$

Where η is the radial ratio between the solid and hollow shaft's radial dimension. As the value of η and κ changes, the structural properties of the shaft change significantly.

- **Case 3:** $r_{\text{solid}} < r_{\text{outer,hollow}}$

In the case when hollow shaft is greater than solid shaft the same appraoch is taken but now η value will be less than one in accordance with our design constraint that radius of solid shaft must be greater than inner radius of hollow shaft.

$$r_{\text{outer}} = \kappa r_{\text{inner}}$$

$$\kappa > 1$$

$$r_{\text{solid}} = \eta r_{\text{outer,hollow}}$$

$$\eta < 1$$

$$\kappa > \frac{1}{\eta}$$

for this configuration the ineqaulity between η and κ must hold to fulfil the design requirements.

5.1 System Configurations

The CAD models of all the three configurations are shown

Figure 2: CAD model of system configurations.

6 Analytical Solution

6.1 Theoretical Calculations

Torque Reactions

A shaft of total length $L = 2\text{ m}$ is fixed at ends A and B . It is subjected to torques at intermediate points:

- Segments: AC, CD, DE, EB each of length 0.5 m .
- Torques applied:

$$T_C = +700\text{ Nm} \quad (\text{counterclockwise})$$

$$T_E = -700\text{ Nm} \quad (\text{clockwise})$$

- Cross-section properties:
 - Segment AD (solid): radius r_{solid} .
 - Segment DB (hollow): outer radius r_{outer} , inner radius r_{inner} .

The shaft is statically indeterminate. The goal is to find reaction torques T_A and T_B at supports using the principle of superposition.

Polar Moments of Inertia

$$J_{\text{solid}} = \frac{\pi r_{\text{solid}}^4}{2}$$

$$J_{\text{hollow}} = \frac{\pi(r_{\text{outer}}^4 - r_{\text{inner}}^4)}{2}$$

Approach: Superposition Method

Remove support A and replace it with unknown reaction torque T_A . Apply the principle:

$$\varphi_{\text{load}} + \varphi_{\text{reaction}} = 0$$

where φ is the angle of twist between A and B .

Internal Torque Diagram

Tracing internal torques from left to right:

- Segment AC : No applied torque yet $\Rightarrow T = 0$
- Segment CD : After C (torque $+700$ Nm) $\Rightarrow T = +700$ Nm
- Segment DE : Same torque $\Rightarrow T = +700$ Nm
- Segment EB : After E (torque -700 Nm) $\Rightarrow T = 0$

Twist Due to Applied Loads φ_{load}

Using:

$$\varphi = \int_0^L \frac{T(x)}{GJ(x)} dx$$

and since torque is constant over each segment:

$$\varphi_{\text{load}} = \sum \frac{T_i L_i}{GJ_i}$$

Explicitly:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{\text{load}} &= \frac{(0)(0.5)}{GJ_{\text{solid}}} + \frac{(700)(0.5)}{GJ_{\text{solid}}} + \frac{(700)(0.5)}{GJ_{\text{hollow}}} + \frac{(0)(0.5)}{GJ_{\text{hollow}}} \\ &= \frac{350}{G} \left(\frac{1}{J_{\text{solid}}} + \frac{1}{J_{\text{hollow}}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Twist Due to Reaction Torque $\varphi_{\text{reaction}}$

Reaction torque T_A causes internal torque throughout the shaft:

$$T = T_A \quad (\text{in all segments})$$

Thus:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{\text{reaction}} &= \sum \frac{T_A L_i}{G J_i} \\ &= \frac{T_A(0.5)}{G J_{\text{solid}}} + \frac{T_A(0.5)}{G J_{\text{solid}}} + \frac{T_A(0.5)}{G J_{\text{hollow}}} + \frac{T_A(0.5)}{G J_{\text{hollow}}} \\ &= \frac{T_A}{G} \left(\frac{1}{J_{\text{solid}}} + \frac{1}{J_{\text{hollow}}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Superposition Condition

Apply:

$$\varphi_{\text{load}} + \varphi_{\text{reaction}} = 0$$

Substituting:

$$\frac{350}{G} \left(\frac{1}{J_{\text{solid}}} + \frac{1}{J_{\text{hollow}}} \right) + \frac{T_A}{G} \left(\frac{1}{J_{\text{solid}}} + \frac{1}{J_{\text{hollow}}} \right) = 0$$

Multiply through by G :

$$(350 + T_A) \left(\frac{1}{J_{\text{solid}}} + \frac{1}{J_{\text{hollow}}} \right) = 0$$

Since $\left(\frac{1}{J_{\text{solid}}} + \frac{1}{J_{\text{hollow}}} \right) \neq 0$, we must have:

$$T_A = -350 \text{ Nm}$$

Finding Reaction Torque at B

From static equilibrium:

$$\sum T = 0$$

Considering all applied and reaction torques:

$$T_A + T_C + T_E + T_B = 0$$

Substituting known values:

$$(-350) + 700 + (-700) + T_B = 0$$

Simplifying:

$$T_B = 350 \text{ Nm}$$

Support Reactions

$T_A = -350 \text{ Nm}$	(Clockwise)
$T_B = +350 \text{ Nm}$	(Counterclockwise)

6.2 Case 1: $r_{\text{solid}} = r_{\text{outer,hollow}}$

Shear Stress Calculations in Shaft

Given:

$$r_{\text{outer}} = r_{\text{solid}}$$

$$r_{\text{outer}} = \kappa r_{\text{inner}} \quad \Rightarrow \quad r_{\text{inner}} = \frac{r_{\text{outer}}}{\kappa}$$

The torque values at supports and sections are:

$$T_A = -350 \text{ Nm} \quad (\text{Clockwise})$$

$$T_B = +350 \text{ Nm} \quad (\text{Counterclockwise})$$

$$T_C = +700 \text{ Nm} \quad (\text{Counterclockwise})$$

$$T_E = -700 \text{ Nm} \quad (\text{Clockwise})$$

Internal torque distribution:

- Segment AC: $T = -350 \text{ Nm}$
- Segment CD: $T = +350 \text{ Nm}$
- Segment DE: $T = +350 \text{ Nm}$
- Segment EB: $T = -350 \text{ Nm}$

Polar moment of inertia for each section:

$$J_{\text{solid}} = \frac{\pi}{2} (\kappa r_{\text{inner}})^4 = \frac{\pi}{2} \kappa^4 r_{\text{inner}}^4$$

$$J_{\text{hollow}} = \frac{\pi}{2} (r_{\text{outer}}^4 - r_{\text{inner}}^4) = \frac{\pi}{2} \left((\kappa r_{\text{inner}})^4 - r_{\text{inner}}^4 \right) = \frac{\pi}{2} r_{\text{inner}}^4 (\kappa^4 - 1)$$

Maximum shear stress in each segment:

Solid Sections (AC and CD):

$$\tau_{\text{AC}} = \frac{T_{\text{AC}} r_{\text{solid}}}{J_{\text{solid}}} = \frac{(-350)\kappa r_{\text{inner}}}{\frac{\pi}{2} \kappa^4 r_{\text{inner}}^4} = -\frac{700}{\pi \kappa^3 r_{\text{inner}}^3}$$

$$\tau_{\text{CD}} = \frac{T_{\text{CD}} r_{\text{solid}}}{J_{\text{solid}}} = \frac{(350)\kappa r_{\text{inner}}}{\frac{\pi}{2} \kappa^4 r_{\text{inner}}^4} = \frac{(350)\kappa r_{\text{inner}}}{\pi \kappa^3 r_{\text{inner}}^3}$$

Hollow Sections (DE and EB):

$$\tau_{\text{DE}} = \frac{T_{\text{DE}} r_{\text{outer}}}{J_{\text{hollow}}} = \frac{(350)\kappa r_{\text{inner}}}{\frac{\pi}{2} r_{\text{inner}}^4 (\kappa^4 - 1)} = \frac{700\kappa}{\pi r_{\text{inner}}^3 (\kappa^4 - 1)}$$

$$\tau_{\text{EB}} = \frac{T_{\text{EB}} r_{\text{outer}}}{J_{\text{hollow}}} = \frac{(-350)\kappa r_{\text{inner}}}{\frac{\pi}{2} r_{\text{inner}}^4 (\kappa^4 - 1)} = -\frac{700\kappa}{\pi r_{\text{inner}}^3 (\kappa^4 - 1)}$$

Final Answer

$\tau_{\text{solid}} = -\frac{700}{\pi \kappa^3 r_{\text{inner}}^3}$
$\tau_{\text{hollow}} = \frac{700\kappa}{\pi r_{\text{inner}}^3 (\kappa^4 - 1)}$

Calculation of Twist Angle φ_{CE} :

First, note that the cross-section dimensions are related as:

$$r_{\text{outer}} = r_{\text{solid}}$$

$$r_{\text{outer}} = \kappa r_{\text{inner}} \quad \Rightarrow \quad r_{\text{solid}} = \kappa r_{\text{inner}}$$

$$r_{\text{solid}}^4 = \kappa^4 r_{\text{inner}}^4$$

The polar moment of inertia for solid section (CD) and hollow section (DE) are used to find the twist separately.

Twist in solid shaft (region CD):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varphi_{CD} &= \frac{T_{CD}L_{CD}}{GJ_{\text{solid}}} \\
 &= \frac{350 \times 0.5}{G \times \frac{\pi}{2} r_{\text{solid}}^4} \\
 &= \frac{350}{G\pi r_{\text{solid}}^4} \\
 &= \frac{350}{G\pi\kappa^4 r_{\text{inner}}^4}
 \end{aligned}$$

Twist in hollow shaft (region DE):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varphi_{DE} &= \frac{T_{DE}L_{DE}}{GJ_{\text{hollow}}} \\
 &= \frac{350 \times 0.5}{G \times \frac{\pi}{2} (r_{\text{outer}}^4 - r_{\text{inner}}^4)} \\
 &= \frac{350}{G\pi (r_{\text{outer}}^4 - r_{\text{inner}}^4)} \\
 &= \frac{350}{G\pi (\kappa^4 r_{\text{inner}}^4 - r_{\text{inner}}^4)} \\
 &= \frac{350}{G\pi r_{\text{inner}}^4 (\kappa^4 - 1)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Total twist between points C and E:

The total twist angle φ_{CE} is the sum of twist angles over regions CD and DE:

$$\boxed{\varphi_{CE} = \varphi_{CD} + \varphi_{DE}}$$

Substituting the expressions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varphi_{CE} &= \frac{350}{G\pi\kappa^4 r_{\text{inner}}^4} + \frac{350}{G\pi r_{\text{inner}}^4 (\kappa^4 - 1)} \\
 &= \frac{350}{G\pi r_{\text{inner}}^4} \left(\frac{1}{\kappa^4} + \frac{1}{\kappa^4 - 1} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying the terms inside the bracket:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{1}{\kappa^4} + \frac{1}{\kappa^4 - 1} &= \frac{(\kappa^4 - 1) + \kappa^4}{\kappa^4(\kappa^4 - 1)} \\
 &= \frac{2\kappa^4 - 1}{\kappa^4(\kappa^4 - 1)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the final simplified expression for twist between C and E is:

$$\varphi_{CE} = \frac{350(2\kappa^4 - 1)}{G\pi r_{\text{inner}}^4 \kappa^4 (\kappa^4 - 1)}$$

6.3 Case 2: $r_{\text{solid}} > r_{\text{outer,hollow}}$

Polar Moment of Inertia expressions (with steps):

For the solid shaft (section CD):

Starting from the standard formula for solid circular cross-section:

$$J_{\text{solid}} = \frac{\pi}{2} r_{\text{solid}}^4$$

Substituting $r_{\text{solid}} = \eta \kappa r_{\text{inner}}$:

$$J_{\text{solid}} = \frac{\pi}{2} (\eta \kappa r_{\text{inner}})^4$$

Simplifying:

$$J_{\text{solid}} = \frac{\pi}{2} \eta^4 \kappa^4 r_{\text{inner}}^4$$

For the hollow shaft (section DE):

$$J_{\text{hollow}} = \frac{\pi}{2} (\kappa^4 - 1) r_{\text{inner,hollow}}^4$$

Shear Stresses

Same as previous formulas, the shear stress for the solid and hollow sections are:

For the solid shaft:

$$\tau_{\text{solid}} = \frac{350 \times r_{\text{solid}}}{J_{\text{solid}}}$$

Substituting:

$$\tau_{\text{solid}} = \frac{700}{\pi \eta^3 \kappa^3 r_{\text{inner}}^3}$$

For the hollow shaft:

$$\tau_{\text{hollow}} = \frac{350 \times r_{\text{outer}}}{J_{\text{hollow}}}$$

Substituting:

$$\tau_{\text{hollow}} = \frac{700\kappa}{\pi(\kappa^4 - 1)r_{\text{inner}}^3}$$

$\tau_{\text{solid}} = \frac{700}{\pi \eta^3 \kappa^3 r_{\text{inner}}^3}$
$\tau_{\text{hollow}} = \frac{700\kappa}{\pi(\kappa^4 - 1)r_{\text{inner}}^3}$

Twist Angle φ_{CE} :

The twist angle between points C and E is calculated by using same approach and putting ratios:

$$\varphi_{CE} = \frac{350 (\kappa^4(1 + \eta^4) - 1)}{G\pi\kappa^4(\kappa^4 - 1)\eta^4 r_{\text{inner}}^4}$$

$$\varphi_{CE} = \frac{350 (\kappa^4(1 + \eta^4) - 1)}{G\pi\kappa^4(\kappa^4 - 1)\eta^4 r_{\text{inner}}^4}$$

6.4 Case 3: $r_{\text{solid}} < r_{\text{outer,hollow}}$

When $r_{\text{solid}} < r_{\text{outer,hollow}}$, the expression for φ_{CE} remains the same as above.

However, in this case:

$$\eta < 1$$

$$\kappa > \frac{1}{\eta}$$

6.5 Graphical Representation of Theoretical Results

The maximum shear stress and twist angle expressions involved are function of radial dimensions , η and κ .

Figure 3: (a) Surface plot of shear stress distribution. (b) Surface plot of angle of twist distribution.

In first case the maximum shear stress and twist angle produced in the shaft is function of inner radius of hollow shaft and radial ratio between inner and outer radius. As the inner radius and radial ratio is decreased so shear stresses increases significantly. The angle of twist is very high for smaller values of radius and radial ratio. Optimized results are obtained by iterating for design constraints.

Figure 4: Surface plot of shear Stress distributions with radial ratios

In second and third configuration the maximum shear stress produced is function of κ , η and inner radius of hollow shaft it shows that for the smaller values of κ and inner radius the stress produced are maximum. The optimized design is selected by iterations based on design constraints and requirements.

6.6 Design Iterations and Final Design

The results obtained from theoretical calculations are used to perform design iterations in accordance with design constraints. The equations obtained from the results are modeled in the python programming language and algorithm is developed to iterate the design based on constraints by varying the radial ratios. Final design is selected based on design requirements and minimul material utilization.

Design #	κ	η	r_{inner} (mm)	τ_{max} (MPa)	φ_{ce} ($^{\circ}$)	FoS
1	1.33	1	15	40.75	3.64	6.7
2	1.30	1.31	20	18.82	0.97	14.6
3	1.3	1	20	19.51	1.31	14.1
4	1.4	0.86	25	8.26	0.51	22.4
5	1.5	0.83	20	26.74	0.97	10.3
6	1.11	1.2	27	24	0.98	11.5
7	1.5	1	20	10.3	0.65	22.4
8	1.4	1.14	25	7.03	0.31	39.1
9	1.67	1	18	9.49	0.63	22.4
10	1.75	1	20	5.82	0.33	35.6

Table 1: Design Iteration Coefficients

6.6.1 Selected Configuration and Design

Based on the algorithm developed for optimized design the selected configuration have following parameters based on the minimum material utilization and satisfying all design constraints :

- $\kappa = 1.3$
- $\eta = 1$
- $r_{\text{inner}} = 20 \text{ mm}$
- $r_{\text{outer}} = 26 \text{ mm}$

This configuration is selected as it satisfies all the design constraints and it is optimized in terms of material utilization.

6.6.2 Cross-Sectional Dimensions

The cross-sectional drawing is created using Solidworks. This drawing represents the bimetallic shaft with solid and hollow section. The solid and hollow shafts have same radius the cross-sectional dimensions are of both shafts are drawn in it.

Figure 5: Cross Sectional Dimensions of Selected Design

All the dimensions are in **mm**.

6.6.3 Maximum Shear Stress and Location

The maximum shear stress occurs in the hollow shaft due to its geometrical properties. The maximum shear stress occurs near the fixed supports of the hollow shaft.

6.6.4 Angle of Twist

The angle of twist φ_{CE} is calculated based on the sum of twist angles in section CD and DE. The larger twist occurs in the hollow shaft at E as compared to Solid shaft in which max twist

occurs at C.

6.6.5 Factor of Safety

The factor of safety is calculated on basis of maximum shear stress occurred throughout the shaft. Among the two FoS for solid and hollow shafts the smaller one is considered for design constraint verification to ensure the structural stability of system.

6.6.6 Reactions at Supports A and B

The reactions at the fixed support A and B are calculated based using the principle of superposition considering the angle of twist from one support to other as zero.

7 FEA Analysis

7.1 Model Details

The model analysis is performed in the ANSYS APDL to evaluate the stress and deformation behaviour of torsionally loaded bimetallic shaft. The **2 node beam 188** is used it includes both bending and shear deformation effects that make it suitable to be used in analysis. The quadratic formulation is used that gives suitable accuracy and optimized results. The static linear model of material is selected in analysis with isotropic properties, so the properties of material is taken same in all direction it simplifies analysis but it is still great to use for many engineering materials.

7.2 Boundary Conditions

The boundary conditions applied in the analysis include the application of torques and displacement constraints. The loading conditions are applied on nodes torques are applied at C and E node of same magnitude but opposite in direction. At point C counter clockwise torque is applied and at E in the clockwise direction. The node A and B are taken as fixed support by taking displacement for all degree of freedom as zero, so all the displacement linear, rotational etc are zero. These combination of torque and rotational constraints provide the suitable modelling of problem and solves the problem.

7.3 Meshing Details

The analysis performed in the APDL by developing the structural model manually by defining the direct node and element definitions without using the automatic meshing tools. The total 5 nodes were created to form 4 **2 nodes BEAM 188** elements. This model is suitable for application required.

Figure 6: Nodes and Elements

7.4 Result Plots

The structural properties are plotted in APDL after simulations. The contour plots of required properties are obtained that shows the behaviour of statically indeterminate torsionally loaded bimetallic shaft.

7.4.1 Support Reactions

The support reactions at the fixed supports of shafts are calculated analytically first and the results obtained from the ANSYS APDL simulations verifies the solution. The reaction torques produced in our case are independent of radial properties of the shaft and depends on the shaft length and material properties. As for any configuration of shaft with same length of sections the reactions are same.

```

PRINT MX REACTION SOLUTIONS PER NODE
***** POST1 TOTAL REACTION SOLUTION LISTING *****
LOAD STEP= 1 SUBSTEP= 1
TIME= 1.0000 LOAD CASE= 0
THE FOLLOWING X,Y,Z SOLUTIONS ARE IN THE GLOBAL COORDINATE SYSTEM
  NODE      MX
   1     -350.00
   5      350.00
TOTAL VALUES
VALUE      0.0000
  
```

Figure 7: Support Reactions of Shaft

7.4.2 Shear Stress Distribution Across Shaft

The shear stress distribution across the shaft shows that maximum shear stress occurs in the hollow shaft near the fixed support. The stress distribution remains uniform through out the shaft except near the supports due to resistance to any displacement at fixed supports. It shows that twist increases as we move toward the point of application of torques in the shaft.

Figure 8: Shear Stress Distribution

7.4.3 Angle of Twist Distribution Across Shaft

The angle of twist distribution across the shaft is plotted. It shows that maximum twist occurs at point of application of torques on the shaft. The maximum twist occurs in the hollow shaft at E and the in the solid shaft at C. The twisting angle distribution is a function of length of sections, torques applied and radial dimensions of the shaft, so the twist produced in the hollow shaft is larger due to its polar moment of inertia in this case that is less as compared to the solid shaft.

twisting angle near the supports is uniform and increases toward the torques applied on the shaft. At the interface eher both shaft angle is nominal but for structural stability and safety proper bonding mechanism between both shafts is required.

Figure 9: Angle of Twist Distribution Across Shaft

7.5 Analysis of FEA Results

The results from the FEA analysis shows reasonable behaviour as compared to analytical results. there are less errors in the maximum shear stress distribution, but for angle of twist less than 5% of errors occurred.

- **Angle of Twist (φ_{ce}):**
 - From APDL: $\varphi_{ce}^{APDL} = 1.252^\circ$
 - Analytical: $\varphi_{ce}^{analytical} = 1.31^\circ$
- **Maximum Shear Stress (τ_{max}):**
 - From APDL: $\tau_{max}^{APDL} = 19.5 \text{ MPa}$
 - Analytical: $\tau_{max}^{analytical} = 19.51 \text{ MPa}$

7.5.1 Percentage Error Calculations

The percentage error is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Percentage Error} = \left| \frac{\text{Analytical} - \text{APDL}}{\text{Analytical}} \right| \times 100$$

- **Angle of Twist Error:**

$$\text{Error}_\varphi = \left| \frac{1.31 - 1.252}{1.31} \right| \times 100 = 4.43\%$$

- **Shear Stress Error:**

$$\text{Error}_\tau = \left| \frac{19.5 - 19.51}{19.5} \right| \times 100 = 0.051\%$$

The APDL results

7.6 Reasons for Difference Between Analytical and APDL Results

7.6.1 Modeling Assumptions and Idealizations

Analytical models for the analysis depends on the idealistic assumptions like complete homogeneity, isotropic behaviour and linear elasticity, but in the FEA analysis using ANSYS APDL it may incorporate realistic or in-depth behaviour of materials. The modelling assumptions causes the difference between results.

7.6.2 Boundary Conditions

In theoretical calculations the boundary conditions are quite simplified, but in FEA analysis it is more precise that can cause possible deviation between results.

7.6.3 Discretization (Mesh) Errors

The ANSYS APDL solution is based on the finite element method that involves the discretization of the body. The accuracy of FEA analysis depends on the mesh density and quality. Irregular meshes can cause the errors that differs from theoretical values.

7.6.4 Numerical Approximation Error

FEA analysis tools like APDL use numerical solvers that transforms the differential equations in to linear equation using different mathematical techniques. These transformation depends on iterations limits, and can cause errors.

7.6.5 Simplifications in Analytical Methods

The analytical solutions doesn't consider the complexities involved to make problem managable. That includes neglecting stress concentrations and different failure behaviours.

8 Conclusion

The design and analysis of statically indeterminate torsionally loaded bimetallic shaft shows the behaviour and optimized design for applications. Depending on the radial ratios between solid and hollow shaft and hollow shafts inner and outer radial dimensions the different cases are configured to optimize the design. The maximum stress and twisting angle based on the constraints are calculated and for verification of results FEA analysis is performed using APDL that shows the significance of the study. The study can be enhanced by including other loading

mechanism with torsion and considering the different failure mechanism along with the shear failire.

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